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First Record of White-Faced Whistling Duck *Dendrocygna Viduata* (Linnaeus, 1766) in Cyrenaica the Eastern Region of Libya

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ABSTRACT: On 25th August 2025, a White-faced Whistling Duck *Dendrocygna viduata* was observed in the Kroom Alkhayl area (32°04'17.2"N 23°50'04.7"E), approximately 12 km west of Tobruk City, eastern Libya. This constitutes the second national record of the species in Libya, following the first observation in 2022 at Al-Saket sewage treatment lagoon, Misrata in Tripolitania (Elsowayeb & Etayeb, 2022). This new record also represents the first for eastern Libya, indicating a probable eastward extension of the species' occurrence within the country.

KEYWORDS: *Dendrocygna viduata*, White-faced Whistling Duck, Tobruk, Cyrenaica; Libya.

INTRODUCTION

The White-faced Whistling Duck *Dendrocygna viduata* (Linnaeus, 1766) is a gregarious waterfowl distributed mainly in sub-Saharan Africa, Madagascar, Comoro Islands, and South America, from Costa Rica and Trinidad to northern Argentina and Uruguay (Johnsgard, 1965; Del Hoyo *et al.*, 1992; Arlott *et al.*, 2021). The species is categorized as Least Concern by the IUCN (BirdLife International, 2016), but its occurrence in North Africa remains exceptional.

The first record of this species in Libya was reported in May 2022 at the sewage treatment lagoon of Al-Saket, Misrata at the Tripolitania region (32°19'11.0"N 15°00'48.3"E) (Elsowayeb and Etayeb, 2022). Here, we present the second Libyan record of the species, and the first from the eastern region of the country.

RESULTS

On 25th August 2025, one adult White-faced Whistling Duck was observed in Kroom Alkhayl area (32°04'17.2"N 23°50'04.7"E), about 12 km west of Tobruk City in Cyrenaica, eastern Libya. The bird was seen, feeding, then shot by a hunter and photographs were taken for documentation (Fig. 2: a,b).

The diagnostic features included a black neck and head, contrasting white face, long grey bill, and dark body with chestnut flanks, confirming the identification as *D. viduata*.

Fig. 1. a. A lateral view of *D. viduata*

b. Dorsal side of *D. viduata*

DISCUSSION

This new record represents the second confirmed observation of *D. viduata* in Libya, and the first in its eastern part (Cyrenaica). The observation supports the hypothesis of an expanding or irregular vagrancy of the species into North Africa, as previously suggested by records from Iraq (Salim *et al.*, 2020) and Socotra, Yemen (Suleiman, 2020).

Kroom Alkhayl area, being a coastal cultivated habitat, provides suitable conditions for migratory and vagrant waterbirds in order to avoid hunting. This finding highlights the importance of Libyan coastal habitats, particularly the wetlands, both natural and artificial, in supporting regional bird diversity despite increasing anthropogenic pressures (Algadry *et al.*, 2022).

Continued monitoring is necessary to assess whether *D. viduata* will remain a rare vagrant in Libya or establish a more regular presence.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Algadry A., Dorman E., Bourass E. & Etayeb K., 2022. The role of constructed wetlands in the conservation of biodiversity: a case study on birds diversity in Al-Hadba treatment plant, Tripoli, Libya. *Biodiversity Journal*, 13: 627–639.
- 2) Arlott N., van Perlo B., Mata J.R.R., Carrizo G., Chiappe A.A. & Huber L., 2021. *The Complete Birds of the World: Every Species Illustrated*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ.
- 3) BirdLife International, 2016. *Dendrocygna viduata*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. 2016: e.T22679763A92829021.
- 4) Del Hoyo J., Elliott A. & Sargatal J., 1992. *Handbook of the Birds of the World*. Vol. 1. Lynx Edicions, Barcelona. ISBN: 978-84-87334-10-8
- 5) Elsowayeb A. & Etayeb K., 2022. First record of White-faced Whistling Ducks *Dendrocygna viduata* in Libya. *Biodiversity Journal*, 13 (4): 813–816. <https://doi.org/10.31396/Biodiv.Jour.2022.13.4.813.816>
- 6) Johnsgard P.A., 1965. *Handbook of Waterfowl Behavior: Tribe Dendrocygnini (Whistling Ducks)*. University of Nebraska. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/bioscihandwaterfowl>
- 7) Salim M.A., Yassir W.S., Abed S.A., Porter R., Jabbar M.T., Abed L.A., Hadi H.A. & Harbi Z.S., 2020. Observations of White-faced Whistling Duck *Dendrocygna viduata* in Iraq. *Sandgrouse*, 42: 115–117.
- 8) Suleiman A.S., 2020. White-faced Whistling Ducks *Dendrocygna viduata* and breeding Red-knobbed Coots *Fulica cristata* on Socotra – the first records for Yemen. *Sandgrouse*, 42: 282–285.